

1 Major differences between HPV+ and HPV- head and neck cancer.

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3 Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹

4 ¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com

5 Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467

6 East Islip, NY USA 11730

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10 We measured total transcription in HPV+ and HPV- head and neck cancers in vivo to understand
11 fundamental properties of cancers resulting from HPV infection. HPV+ head and neck cancers were
12 Bmpr1b- and Igf1-, while HPV- head and neck cancers were Bmpr1b+ and Igf1+. HPV+ head and neck
13 cancers display unique cell cycle regulatory capacity manifested by differential activation repression of the
14 CDKN family (e.g., CDKN2A) and differential control of CDK enzymes including CDK6. HPV+ head and
15 neck cancers were MMP7- and MMP10- while HPV- head and neck cancers were MMP7+ and MMP10+.
16 Immune receptor composition distinguished head and neck cancers: HPV+ cancers were Ildr1+ but Flrt2-
17 Chemokine and cytokine expression distinguished HPV+ and HPV- head and neck cancers; HPV+ head
18 and neck cancers produced large amounts of Cxcl17 but were Cxcl16- and IL6-. We describe here specific
19 control of Taf transcriptional apparatus marked by selective activation of Taf7I in HPV+ head and neck
20 cancers. HPV+ head and neck cancers were Sox30+ and displayed differential control of the myosin
21 machinery (e.g., Myh14). Junctional composition distinguished head and neck cancers resulting from HPV
22 infection: HPV+ head and neck cancers expressed Tjp3 and were Cldn4+.